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Review Article

Pharmacological and Therapeutic Potential of Suranjān Shīrīn (*Colchicum autumnale* Linn.): A Review from Modern and Unani Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Suranjān Shīrīn (*Colchicum autumnale* Linn.), commonly known as Meadow Saffron or Autumn Crocus, is a well-known medicinal plant in both Unani and modern medicine. Traditionally, it has been widely used in the management of arthritis, gout, and other musculoskeletal disorders. Its corm and flowers are medicinally valuable and are described in Unani literature as possessing Mushil, Musakkin-e-Alam, and Muhallil properties. Modern pharmacological studies have validated its anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, antioxidant, and anticancer properties, largely attributed to its active alkaloid colchicine. However, due to potential toxicity to the stomach and liver, it requires correctives (Muslih) during administration. This review aims to integrate classical Unani references with contemporary pharmacological evidence, highlighting its therapeutic potential, formulations, substitutes, and safety profile.

INTRODUCTION

Dioscorides introduced the Latin term *colchicum*, derived from the district of Colchis on the eastern Black Sea coast. The plant *Colchicum autumnale* Linn. is referred to as *Suranjān Shīrīn* in the Unani system of medicine. It is a perennial hysteroanthous geophyte belonging to the family Colchicaceae

(formerly Liliaceae), commonly known as “Autumn Crocus” or “Meadow Saffron.”

Traditionally, it has been a drug of choice for arthritis in Unani medicine and is prescribed in various formulations for arthritic and joint disorders. It is valued both in polyherbal combinations and as a single drug remedy. ⁽¹⁻⁴⁾

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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This study is a narrative review on *Colchicum autumnale* Linn. (Suranjān Shīrīn). Data were collected from classical Unani texts including *Al-Qānūn fi'l-Ṭibb*, *Al-Hāwī fi'l-Ṭibb*, *Makhzan al-Adwiya*, and others. Modern evidence was retrieved from PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Web of Science using keywords such as *Colchicum autumnale*, *Suranjan*, *colchicine*, and *pharmacological activity*.

Inclusion criteria were original research, reviews, clinical trials, ethnopharmacological studies, and classical references related to *Colchicum autumnale*. Non-relevant and inaccessible articles were excluded. Data on description, Unani uses, pharmacology, and clinical efficacy were compiled and analyzed thematically to compare traditional claims with modern findings.

Habitat

Suranjān Shīrīn is a corm-bearing herb widely distributed in Europe, the Mediterranean region, Central Asia, Northern India (especially Jammu & Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Western Himalayas, Chamba, and Murree Hills). A related species, *Colchicum speciosum* Stev., is reported from Badghis and Khorasan and also used in India. ^(1,5)

Vernacular Names ^(3,6,7,8,9)

Language	Names
Unani	Falheeqaan, Aqeemarooon, Balboosa, Falheeq, Asmaroon, Qabarooro
Arabic	Akba, Laeba Bararbaria, Quln-ul-Arz, Surajan Hulo
Persian	Haqeer, Surangan, Suranjan Shireen, Shambleed
Hindi	Barbari, Jangli Singara, Haran Tuttiya
English	Colchicum, Meadow Saffron
Punjab	Suranjan Talkh
Sanskrit	Hiranya Tutta, Tutham
Kashmiri	Surangan, Virkeum, Moond

Taxonomic Classification ⁽¹⁰⁾

Rank	Classification
Scientific Name	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i> Linn.
Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Liliales
Family	Colchicaceae
Genus	<i>Colchicum</i>
Species	<i>C. autumnale</i>

Fig: Suranjan (Colchicum)

Morphological Description

Suranjān Shīrīn is a perennial herb with a scaly, brown underground corm. In autumn, it bears solitary, tubular violet flowers resembling crocuses but differentiated by six stamens. Flowers measure 7–10 cm in length and 2–4 cm in diameter, with colors ranging from pale violet to crimson or yellow.

In spring, large, glossy green leaves appear in a rosette arrangement surrounding the fruit capsule. Seeds are small (2–3 mm), brown, pitted, and odorless. The corm is fleshy white internally, contains fibrovascular bundles, and has a sharp, bitter taste. The plant is among the first to flower after snow melts. ^(11,12,13,14,15)

Phytochemistry

Major chemical constituents of *Colchicum autumnale* include:⁽⁹⁾

- Colchicine
- Colchicoside
- 3-demethylcolchicine
- Cholchamine
- Cornigerine
- Luteine, Luteidine, Collutine
- Minor components: starch, gum, sugar, resin, tannins, and water (70%)

UNANI DESCRIPTION

Hasas-e-Musta'mila (Parts Used) ^(2,6,11)

- Corm (*Suranjān*)
- Flowers

Mizāj (Temperament) ^(2,6)

- Hot 2° & Dry 2° (*Haar 2°, Yābis 2°*)

Af'āl (Pharmacological Actions in Unani Medicine) ^(2,6,16)

- Mushil (Purgative)
- Qābiz (Constipative)
- Mushil-e-Balgham (Phlegmagogue)
- Musakkin-e-Alam (Analgesic)
- Muhallil (Resolvent)
- Muharrik-e-Baah (Aphrodisiac)
- Mujaffif-e-Qurūh (Desiccant of ulcers)

Istemāl (Therapeutic Uses) ^(2,6,11)

- Waja' al-Mafāšil (Arthralgia/arthritis)
- Niqris (Gout)
- Irq al-Nasā (Sciatica)
- Warm-e-Balghamī (Phlegmatic swellings)
- Yaraqān (Jaundice)
- Nuzūl al-Mā' (Cataract)
- Amrāz-e-Tihāl (Diseases of spleen)
- Kirm-e-Shikam (Intestinal worms)

Miqdār-e-Khurāk (Dose)

- 2.25–3 g ⁽¹²⁾

Muzir (Adverse Effects) and Muslih (Correctives)

- **Muzir (Adverse Effects):** May adversely affect stomach and liver ^(2,6,11).
- **Muslih (Correctives):** Kateera (*Astragalus gummifer*), Qand Safed (Granular sugar), Zafran (*Crocus sativus*), Sonth (*Zingiber officinale*), Filfil Siyah (*Piper nigrum*), Amla Murabba (*Emblica officinalis*) ^(6,16).

Badal (Substitutes) ^(2,6,16)

- Turbud (*Operculina turpethum*)
- Afteemoone Hindi (*Cuscuta reflexa* Roxb.)
- Kharbaq Abyaz (*Veratrum viride* Ait.)
- Hina / Mehndi (*Lawsonia alba*)
- Muqil (*Commiphora mukul*)
- Buzidan (*Tanacetum umbelliferum*)

Mashhūr Murakkab (Famous Formulations) ⁽¹⁷⁾

- Majoon Suranjan
- Habb-e-Dard-e-Mafāšil
- Habb-e-Suranjaan

Pharmacological Actions (Modern Studies) ^(18,19)

1. Anti-arthritis Activity

- Effective in rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and gout.
- Comparable to Diclofenac sodium in anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic effect.
- Clinical trials: Colchicine 0.6 mg twice daily significantly reduced gout crises; in FMF patients, it prevented arthritis flare-ups.

2. Anti-inflammatory Activity

- Zemer et al. (1991): Colchicine (1–2 mg/day) in 350 children with FMF prevented amyloidosis with minimal side effects.

3. Antioxidant Activity

- Ethanollic and chloroform extracts showed strong antioxidant potential (chloroform fraction up to 91% activity).

4. Anticancer Activity

- Lin et al. (2001): Colchicine inhibited proliferation of gastric carcinoma cell lines in a dose-dependent manner and suppressed tumor growth in nude mice.

Activity	Study/Model	Findings
Anti-arthritis	Clinical trial (1987)	Colchicine 0.6 mg ↓ gout crises; effective in RA, OA, gout
Anti-inflammatory	Zemer et al., 1991 (FMF patients)	1–2 mg/day prevented amyloidosis; safe in long-term
Antioxidant	Ahmed et al., 2010	Chloroform extract showed 91% antioxidant activity
Anticancer	Lin et al., 2001 (GC cell lines & mice)	Dose-dependent inhibition of proliferation; ↓ tumor growth

DISCUSSION

The Unani description of *Suranjān Shīrīn* as an analgesic, resolvent, and purgative closely aligns with its modern pharmacological profile. Its primary alkaloid, colchicine, has been validated in randomized controlled trials for arthritis and gout. Unani physicians recognized its adverse effects on the gastrointestinal and hepatic systems, prescribing *Muslih* (correctives) such as ginger and saffron to minimize toxicity, a practice that resonates with modern dose-regulation strategies.

The wide therapeutic spectrum i.e, from arthritis and gout to cancer and oxidative stress, suggests immense potential for drug discovery. However, its narrow therapeutic index and risk of toxicity emphasize the need for standardization, safe formulations, and clinical trials bridging traditional and modern perspectives.

CONCLUSION

Suranjān Shīrīn (*Colchicum autumnale* Linn.) is a time-tested drug in Unani medicine, primarily used in arthritis and joint disorders. Its active alkaloid, colchicine, has been extensively validated for anti-arthritic and anti-inflammatory efficacy. Modern studies also highlight its antioxidant and anticancer activities. Despite its potential, toxicity remains a concern, warranting cautious use with proper correctives and adherence to dose. Integration of traditional knowledge with modern pharmacological validation could provide safer, effective therapeutic applications and open avenues for new drug development.

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